

NOTES

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS (AA) BY DICHLORAMINE-T (DCT) IN 1:1 (v/v) WATER-METHANOL MEDIUM IN PRESENCE OF PERCHLORIC ACID AT 303 K*

[DCT] ₀ × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[AA] ₀ × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[HClO ₄] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	k_{obs} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)	
			Met	Thr
Effect of varying [DCT] ₀				
0.5	2.0(5.0)	10(1.0)	7.7	7.4
1.0	2.0(5.0)	10(1.0)	7.3	7.4
1.5	2.0(5.0)	10(1.0)	7.5	—
2.0	2.0(5.0)	10(1.0)	7.4	7.3
4.0	2.0(5.0)	10(1.0)	7.6	7.0
Effect of varying [AA] ₀				
1.0	0.5	10(1.0)	7.8	—
1.0	1.0	10(1.0)	7.6	2.7
1.0	2.0	10(1.0)	7.3	4.5
1.0	4.0	10(1.0)	7.1	—
1.0	5.0	10(1.0)	—	7.4
1.0	7.0	10(1.0)	—	9.0
1.0	10.0	10(1.0)	—	11.2
Effect of varying [HClO ₄]				
1.0	2.0(5.0)	0.2	—	19.0
1.0	2.0(5.0)	0.5	—	10.4
1.0	2.0(5.0)	1.0	—	7.4
1.0	2.0(5.0)	2.0	—	3.7
1.0	2.0(5.0)	5.0	4.2	2.5
1.0	2.0(5.0)	10.0	7.3	2.0
1.0	2.0(5.0)	20.0	16.0	—
1.0	2.0(5.0)	30.0	24.7	—

*Values in parenthesis are for Thr.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH (I) AND SOLVENT COMPOSITION OF MEDIUM AND ADDITION OF THE REACTION PRODUCT, TOLUENE-*p*-SULPHONAMIDE (TSA) ON RATES OF OXIDATIONS

I mol dm ⁻¹	k_{obs} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)		[TSA] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	k_{obs} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)	
	Met	Thr		Met	Thr
0.2	6.4	7.4	0	7.3	7.4
0.3	6.9	7.4	1.0	7.5	—
0.5	7.3	7.4	3.0	7.4	7.4
% MeOH			4.0	—	7.5
30	9.3	—	5.0	7.3	—
40	8.2	12.1			
50	7.3	7.4			
60	6.7	4.3			

strength of the medium or the addition of toluene-*p*-sulphonamide had negligible or no effect on the rates. Decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by increasing the methanol composition of the solvent decreased the rates. The plots of log k_{obs} vs % methanol were also linear with negative slopes. The rates of reactions were also measured at different temperatures and the activation parameters computed. The values are $-\log A$, 8.10 (Thr), 3.28 (Met); E_a (kJ mol⁻¹), 65.2 (Thr), 37.2 (Met); $\Delta H^\ddagger$ (kJ mol⁻¹), 62.7 (Thr), 32.8 (Met); $\Delta G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol⁻¹), 92.4 (Thr), 59.7 (Met); $\Delta S^\ddagger$ (JK⁻¹), -98.3 (Thr), -197.9 (Met).

Mechanism of oxidation: The observed kinetics of first order in [DCT], fractional order in [Thr] and inverse fractional order in [H⁺] for the oxidation of Thr by DCT may be explained by a mechanism shown in Scheme 1.

SH⁺ (Scheme 1) is protonated Thr. The related rate law is given by equation (3),

$$-\frac{d[\text{DCT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_2 k_3 [\text{DCT}]_0 [\text{S}]}{1 + K_2 [\text{S}]} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{DCT}]_0 [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 [\text{SH}^+]} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{or } k_{obs} = \frac{K_2 k_3 [\text{S}]}{1 + K_2 [\text{S}]} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 [\text{SH}^+]} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{K_2 k_3} \cdot \frac{1}{[\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{k_3} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{SH}^+]} + \frac{1}{k_3} \quad (5)$$

The plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{Thr}]$ was linear (Fig. 1) in accordance with equation (5). From the slope and intercept of the former plot the constants K_2 (23.33) and k_3 (1.43×10^{-8}) were calculated and then K_1 (7.98×10^{-8}) was computed from the slope of the latter plot. Further, k_{obs} vs $[\text{Thr}]$ plot was non-linear (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Plots of (i) k_{obs} vs $[\text{Thr}]_0$ and (ii) $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{Thr}]_0$. $10^3 [\text{DCT}]_0 = 10^3 [\text{HClO}_4] = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 303 K.

The rate was first order each in [DCT] and [H⁺] and zero order in [Met] for methionine oxidation. These results can be accounted by a mechanism shown in Scheme 2. Under the conditions of methionine oxidation ($[\text{H}^+] = 0.05 - 0.30$ mol dm⁻³) it is likely that the oxidant gets protonated facilitating the donation of Cl⁺ species more readily. The latter in turn reacts with the substrate in fast steps.

The corresponding rate law is

$$-\frac{d[\text{DCT}]}{dt} = k_4 [\text{DCT}][\text{H}^+] \quad (6)$$

$$\text{or } k_{\text{obs}} = k_4[\text{H}^+] \quad (7)$$

The plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{H}^+]$ grve a straight line passing through the origin (Fig. not shown).

Detailed mechanism of oxidations of Thr and Met by DCT are similar to chloramine-T oxidations reported elsewhere*.

The observed dielectric effect on the rates of oxidations can be explained by Amis concept⁸, which predicts linearities between $\log k_D$ and $1/D$ with negative slopes for the interaction between two dipoles. The plots of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs % methanol were linear with negative slopes in accordance with this concept.

References

1. M. M. CAMPBELL and G. JOHNSTON, *Chem. Rev.*, 1978, **78**, 65 and references therein; B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1983, 323 and references therein; K. K. BANERJI, B. JAYARAM and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1987, **46**, 65 and references therein; B. T. GOWDA and R. V. RAO, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1988, 355; *Oxidn. Commun.*, 1987, **10**, 31; 1988, **11**, 45, 149; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 1021; 1986, **25**, 578; 1988, **27**, 34, 39; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 403, 467, 474, 1988, **65**, 339; B. T. GOWDA and B. S. SHERIGARA, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1989, **21**, 31; *Oxidn. Commun.*, 1986, **9**, 165; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 960; *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1989, **101**, 155; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 91; B. T. GOWDA and J. I. BHAT, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1986, **31**, 461; *Tetrahedron*, 1987, **43**, 2119; *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1989, **21**, 621; *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1988, **100**, 275; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 1129, 1149; 1987, **26**, 215; 1988, **27**, 597, 786; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 665; 1988, **65**, 159.
2. B. T. GOWDA and P. RAMACHANDRA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans 2*, 1989, 1067; *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1990, **102**, 3303.
3. B. T. GOWDA and B. S. SHERIGARA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 930; B. T. GOWDA and J. I. BHAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 150; B. T. GOWDA and P. J. M. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 151
4. B. T. GOWDA and P. J. M. RAO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn*, 1989, **62**.
5. T. J. JACOB and C. G. R. NAIR, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 347.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Organic Analysis", Longman Green, London, 1978.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "Qualitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman, London, 1978; "Vogel's Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry" eds. B. S. FURNISS, A. J. HANNAFORD, V. ROGGER, P. W. G. SMITH and A. R. TATCHELL, Longman, London, 1978.
8. E. S. AMIS, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic, New York, 1966.

Excess Volumes of Binary Solutions of 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane with some Ketones at 313.15 K

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In order to investigate the variation in the thermodynamic properties of binary mixtures resulting from isomeric changes in the configuration of component molecules we have been determining excess functions of isomeric compounds in different solvents^{1,2}. In continuation of the above studies we report here excess volumes of five binary systems consisting of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane with different ketones at 313.15 K over entire mole fraction range for each system.

Experimental

2,2,4-Trimethylpentane, dimethyl ketone, isobutyl methyl ketone, acetylacetone and cyclohexanone (L. R. grade) were used after distillation. Cyclohexane (Merck for synthesis) was used as such. The density and boiling point of the pure liquids compared well with the literature values³. The details of the method adopted have been described elsewhere⁴.

Results and Discussion

Excess volumes per mole (V^E) for the mixtures were calculated using the relation,

$$V^E = (M_1x_1 + M_2x_2)/d - M_1x_1/d_1 - M_2x_2/d_2 \quad (1)$$

where M_i , x_i and d_i represent the molecular weight, mole fraction and density respectively of the component i ($i = 1, 2$) and d is the density of the solution.

Excess volumes for the studied binary solutions are given in Table I. For the systems 2,2,4-trimethylpentane+dimethyl ketone, +isobutyl methyl ketone, and +acetylacetone the excess volumes are positive and nearly symmetrical throughout the studied mole fraction range (Fig. 1). For the system 2,2,4-trimethylpentane+cyclohexanone the excess volumes are negative. In case of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane+cyclohexane system the excess volumes are negligibly small exhibiting sigmoid plot having negative values at 0-0.2 mole fraction of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane and positive values at the remaining mole fraction.

Effect of R (alkyl) group: Excess volumes of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane+isobutyl methyl ketone are lower than the system 2,2,4-trimethylpentane+dimethyl ketone. This may be due to the favourable interstitial accommodation of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane within the larger alkyl group of isobutyl ketone in comparison to smaller alkyl group in dimethyl ketone which results in negative contribution